

A Comprehensive Review of Irrigation Practices and Challenges in Bangladesh: Pathways to Sustainable Agricultural Productivity

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Abstract:

Crop water is a critical input in any farming systems across the globe, especially in the developing countries in South Asia where appropriate water management in the farming systems remains a major challenge such as in the case of Bangladesh. This review also aimed at describing changes in the status and the perspective of the irrigation systems in Bangladesh. This shift in the water resource base from surface water irrigation to groundwater in the early 1980s paved way to ensure food self-sufficiency, a feat the country accomplished in the early 1990s. But with the increased use of groundwater sources there have been some questions on the sustainability of this source, this has seen a shift back to surface

water and better irrigation techniques and practices like micro-irrigation, drips and auto irrigation. This paper aims to review the global practices of irrigation, practicing a contrast between gravity irrigators and pressurized irrigators, besides also focusing on the opportunities and risks of the drip irrigation especially in the arid zones. It also reviews the critical issues confronted by Bangladesh such as climate change, water sector problem, and water saving irrigation system. The discoveries advise that smart water irrigation technologies should be included for better efficiency for irrigation in Bangladesh so that productivity is not checked in the coming future. With regards to this, it is the hope of this review to pinpoint the areas to be enhanced so as to support policy and practice for the enhancement of the management of water resources as well as meeting the needs of the agricultural sector in the future.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Irrigation, Groundwater depletion, Drip irrigation, Climate change, Agricultural productivity.

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Introduction

The global population which is constant growing require food, energy, and water which is projected to increase by 50%, 50%, and 30%, respectively in 2030 from 2012 (Islam & Karim, 2019). Projections for the same are 70% to 100% higher in 2050 as compared to the base (Bank, 2013). Bangladesh is thought to host around 2.7 percent of the total global population; this makes it ranking eighth in the world based on population size. According to the Census records as 2022, the total population of Bangladesh is 169,828,911 persons (Manik, 2024). Irrigation is a very vital component that has been used to improve productivity in the agricultural sector since water is often a limiting factor in areas such as south-central coastal zone of Bangladesh. Application of Sustainable Irrigation Management in Agriculture (Palma & Tomaz, 2024). Sustainable agriculture like intercropping could help farmers manage resources more efficiently hence enhancing economic growth and Gemeinschaft in the farmer's micro world by providing the means of sustainable productivity (Begam et al., 2024). Intercropping: the opportunities and threats in Bangladesh for sustainable agriculture. Journal: international journal of engineering applied science and technology, (Akter et al.). As it has been seen with the practices of irrigation, the related implications like salinity of water and climate change effects on crops like 'Boro' rice need to be urgently worked on to optimize irrigation effects (Jamal et al., 2023). Is there the possibility of crop production intensification with the help of irrigation? An ex-ante impact study of the coastal zone of Bangladesh by (Khan et al., 2023). Strengthening adaptation in coastal Bangladesh: for sustainable agriculture and water management for the development of desirable community based interventions. Adaptable measures such as rainwater harvesting can reduce the scarcity of water and salinity as a problem leading to sustainable Agriculture (Shapna et al., 2024). Strengthening adaptation in coastal Bangladesh: solutions such as community-based initiatives in regard to sustainable agriculture and water utilization.

Through the provision of the foregoing by ensuring appropriate extension services, farmer education, and policy intervention, Bangladesh can improve its agricultural productivity, cut down on costly inputs, and increase farmers' income levels hence helping to achieve poverty alleviation and rural development (Shapna et al., 2024). Intercropping: Opportunities and risks for the sustainable use of agriculture in Bangladesh. International journal of civil and structural engineering. Strengthening adaptation in coastal Bangladesh: sustainable agriculture, water conservation, water management and micro-level appropriate Technologies and people's participation through community based initiatives. What is more, Bangladesh inhabits one of the highest population densities on the globe at the present stage. The TFR has decreased by a value greater than 2/3 in the over half a century following the attaining of independence. Bangladesh Total Fertility Rate is now 1.930 per woman, this is considered to lie below the global average for replacement level fertility (Bora et al., 2019). Majority of the population of Bangladesh still lives in the rural areas; they live in small farming villages, typical of areas that can support rice cultivation (Rahman et al., 2020). With an estimated 38. Currently, 2% of the population living in cities, urbanization has occurred. It is identified that around 65.6% areas of total geographical area of Bangladesh is occupied by Agricultural land (Ullah & Uddin, 2021). Out of this total, 65 percent is used in farming of permanent crops and the other 59 percent for other crops. 2% is arable. Besides, pastures and meadows occupy 4% of the territory of the district. Notably, less acreage is available for farming due to the fact that more land owners are now practicing very small units of farming of less than an acre. Also, only half of the area identified as forest a little over one-seventh of the country can really be considered wooded (Amelia et al., 2023). The River system in Bangladesh is divided into three categories based on their geographical region; The middle and Northern regions of the country falls under subtropical region while the southern region of Bangladesh falls under Tropical

region(Uddin et al., 2020). The country experiences mild winter that is sunny to some extent in most parts of the country; slightly cooler in the northern region and relatively warmer in the southern region. The wet season is experienced between June and October due to the impact of the summer monsoon while spring is experienced between March and May and which is dry and hot. About climate in South East Asia – much heat, a lot of rainfall, high humidity, and the clear separation of seasons(Alam et al., 2023). Bangladesh can be described as having a warm and humid climate and bears the effects of pre-during and post monsoon. Formerly, average temperature has been ranging about 26oC, with extremes ranging between 15 to 34 oC on annual basis. While the rainy season ranges from April to September, summer and autumn are the hottest periods, on the other hand, winter is from December to February and is considerably colder and less wet(Shirin et al., 2022). Bangladesh gets an average of 2,200 millimeters (mm) of rainfall annually putting it in the league of the most rainy countries in the world. The most of locales receive more than 1,500 mm of rain per year however certain border territories of the northeast obtain up to 5,000 mm(Ahmed et al., 2020). Agriculture plays a pivotal role for Bangladesh as it is the strongest engine of the country's economy by providing massive employment for the employees and a big portion of the country's gross domestic product. But as the other sectors of the economy have developed, their contribution in relation to agriculture has been declining (Safa & Ories, 2023). About 35 million people in Bangladesh are still living in poverty even though incremental development in economic, poverty elimination and human development was observed in the last decades(Mahmud, 2008). It has been known from different studies that enlargement of the agricultural sector is required to improve the poverty rate of the country(Bell et al., 2015). Most of the population of the nation is involved in agricultural activities, and they cultivate numerous crops, and the country is an agricultural country by majority (Samanta Chandan & Roy, 2024; Tahrim et al., 2023). There are three principal cropping seasons,

namely, aman Boro and aus used to produce out a range of four types of rice which is the staple diet and the biggest income earner constituting more than 50% of the total income in agriculture(Bir et al., 2024). The problems includes; Climate change which poses several dangers which includes endangering productivity and health of the soil, soil erosion and water deficiency, high production rates exploited by favourable climate conditions(Ashraf, 2023; Michael et al., 2023). But for generations, the farmers of Bangladesh have been more into using irrigation for growing crops, which from using hand scoop and surface water to something much more modern. To increase the irrigation efficiency that is vital in maintaining the agricultural production that is needed for the country's food security, the following was suggested; Currently, like many other countries, Bangladesh utilizes the traditional and modern ways of irrigation including the surface irrigation, groundwater irrigation and the recently popularized drip and sprinkler irrigation systems(Hossain et al., 2024). Thus, many structures of irrigation still need repair and further development in spite of these improvements. Several problems prevail in irrigation systems of this nation – recurring floods, saline water intrusion into the coastal zones, water scarcity in the dry season, and the existing inefficient methods that involve wastage of water(Ahsan, 2023). (Haque & Nahar, 2023) has explained that climate change hampers the management of water resources because has unpredictable weather condition. Actually irrigation techniques for instance sprinkler and drip techniques have enhanced water usage in the recent past. Because access must be optimised and wastage minimised, automation and smart watering systems are being introduced(Kanimozhi & Vadivel, 2024). Efficient irrigation practices call for supports from the government initiatives including; financing of modern irrigation practices and farmer education(BBS, 2021). To-date, research institutes in Bangladesh have played a significant role in developing DRAP Approach to agriculture sometimes collaboratively with overseas bodies(Hossain & Bari, 2022).The study intends to provide a comprehensive

scenario analysis of Bangladesh's Irrigation Technology at the existing state. It will analyse how the long and short term techniques used for irrigation have evolved, what performance the today's techniques offer, examine at the new technology available in the field and look at the issues that exist. Thus, it is expected that this research will be able to raise awareness about how crucial irrigation is for Bangladesh's crop production and keeping the sector secure.

Literature Review

Historical Evolution of Irrigation Practices in Bangladesh

Bangladesh's irrigation systems have evolved historically, reflecting a dynamic interaction between ancient techniques and contemporary advances meant to meet the nation's particular agricultural difficulties. In the past, Bangladeshi farmers used low lift pumps and other antiquated equipment to irrigate their farms (Table 1), mostly relying on surface water sources such rivers and ponds (Mou et al., 2023). But a big change came with the introduction of groundwater irrigation in the late 20th century, which allowed farmers to grow rice fields in the dry season and become self-sufficient in food by the 1990s (Samanta Chandan & Roy, 2024). Though beneficial, this heavy groundwater usage raised worries about over-abstraction and groundwater depletion, which prompted the government to look into alternate strategies such surface water irrigation made possible by rubber dams (Haque & Nahar, 2023). By installing deep tube wells, excavating water bodies, and building check dams to improve groundwater recharge and surface water conservation, the Barind Multipurpose Development Authority (BMDA) significantly contributed to the transformation of the barren Barind Tract into a fertile area (Safa & Ories, 2023). At the same time, innovations in technology have been made to enhance water usage efficiency and minimize waste, such as automated micro irrigation systems and fuzzy neural network-controlled irrigation controllers (Alam et al., 2023; Rahman & Connor, 2024). Given that climate change has increased rainfall

unpredictability and necessitated more effective water management, these advances are especially significant. Studies have also highlighted the potential of wastewater irrigation as a viable adaptation strategy to cope with water scarcity (Mallareddy et al., 2023). Research on the use of river water in coastal areas to irrigate dry season crops such as Boro rice has shown that, under scenarios of mild climate change, there would be no effect on the salinity of the rivers (Mitra et al., 2023). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that optimizing irrigation scheduling with models such as CROPWAT maximizes crop output by coordinating transplanting dates with times of greater effective rainfall, hence minimizing the requirement for additional irrigation (Khan et al., 2023). Even with these developments, problems with funding, equipment scarcity, and farmer education remain, requiring ongoing efforts to supply affordable irrigation equipment and offer skill-building initiatives (Mou et al., 2023). Overall, the necessity to strike a balance between agricultural output and water resource conservation has led to a steady transition in Bangladeshi irrigation techniques from conventional methods to more advanced and sustainable ways (Merza et al., 2023). Today, tubewells supply safe drinking water to 97% of Bangladesh's rural population, with groundwater serving as the main source for both irrigation and drinking. Roughly 80% of the irrigation water utilized during the dry season originates from groundwater (Ahmed et al., 2012).

Current State of Irrigation Infrastructure in Bangladesh

At present, Bangladesh has started constructing its irrigation system through the conventional methods together with the modern techniques with a concentration on sustainability and effectiveness. While common irrigation and many others types of irrigation methods are still in use today, they are very often inefficient and cause a lot of water to be wasted. Owing to this, many contemporary irrigation systems are being used in solving this.

Table 1. Evolution of irrigation practices in Bangladesh

Period	Key technology and project	Impact and development
Pre-colonial Sultanate Regime up to the year 1757	Water reservoir irrigation: Rivers, reservoirs, tanks, channels, creeks, backwaters, valleys Improved fertilizer output.	Control of floods, and consequent improved increase in agricultural yields and general development of the region.
British Regime (post-1757)	The advancements in the agricultural field started to decline	The main concern shifted towards water transportation, there were reversals in the progress of horticulture.
1954-55	Ganges-Kobadak (G-K) 3,105	Began the first major irrigation project that is considered as a milestone in the development of agricultural undertaking.
1959	Creation of a legal entity as a national organization, namely the Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB).	Implemented many irrigation projects like DND, Thakurgaon DTW and enhanced irrigation structures.
1962	Bangladesh Agricultural Development Corporation (BADC) formed	improvements in irrigation through the construction of low level permutations (LLPs) and detailed water (DTWs); overhauls in conservation and liberalization of products such as seeds and fertilizers.
Mid 1960s	Availability of portable water through Hand Tubewells (HTWs) with the support from UNICEF	First used for the purpose of getting portable water for drinking and later on they were used for irrigation which helped the farmers to raise Rice Production to a large extent.
Late 1960s	The introduction of HYV rice GIT	Development of HYV rice such as IR-8 and the use of HTWs for irrigation to boost productivity.
1971-72	Expansion of the Shallow Tubewell (STW) irrigation system	Major initiative by BADC to increase irrigated areas, leading to a boost in food grain production.
1995	Rubber dams constructed in Cox's Bazar by LGED	Innovative water resource management technique to enhance irrigation for boro rice.
Early 1970s and 1990s	Shift from Deep Tubewells (DTWs) to Shallow Tubewells (STWs)	Affordability due to liberal import policies led to widespread adoption of STWs.
Early 2000s	Decline in use of Manual Pumps	Shift towards more efficient irrigation technologies, reducing reliance on manual methods.

Table 2. The Impact of Three Treatments on the Efficiency of Water Use

Treatment	Total water used (mm)	Pod Yield (t/ha)	Water Use Efficiency (kg/m ³)	Water savings (%)
Control treatment	145	15.57	10.74	-
Improve Efficiency	132	16.46	12.47	9
Optimized Performance	129	16.7	12.95	11

Note: Adapted from "Effect of Irrigation Levels on Pod Yield and Water Use Efficiency in Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea L.*)" by (Zannat et al., 2023)

Control Treatment: This treatment established the baseline for the study, utilizing 145 mm of water. The results showed a pod yield of 15.57 tons per hectare and a water use efficiency of 10.74 kg/m³. This scenario reflects standard irrigation practices without any modifications for water savings.

Improved Efficiency: In this treatment reduced the water usage to 132 mm, refining the irrigation process to enhance efficiency. The modifications led to an increased pod yield of 16.46 tons per hectare and a water use efficiency of 12.47 kg/m³. It achieved a 9% reduction in water usage compared to T1, indicating the success of the implemented water-saving

techniques.

Optimized Performance: This represents the most advanced treatment with a further reduced water usage of 129 mm. It yielded the highest pod production of 16.70 tons per hectare and the greatest water use efficiency at 12.95 kg/m³, with an 11% water savings. This treatment utilized state-of-the-art irrigation technology, possibly incorporating precision irrigation and real-time soil moisture monitoring, to ensure optimal water usage and enhanced crop productivity.

Timer drip irrigation is among the micro irrigation systems which include;(Zannat et al., 2023) and have been established to use water more efficiently, 11% more efficiently than conventional methods (Table 2). BMDA has already incorporated proper water management practices to meet the calamity of drought that frequently found in the Barind Tract. Such measures, which have enhanced the recharging of bore wells and brought about revolutionary change in the field of irrigation, are deep tube well, pond/ canal re-excavation and construction of check dam(Ali et al., 2023). Furthermore, there is the introduction of what is being referred to as photovoltaic systems as a better solution to the grid-and diesel-based systems. These solar systems can reduce energy cost and water consumption by 50 to 60 percent if integrated with a fuzzy logic controller(Ghalib et al., 2023). Also, the government has set objectives to increase the capability of solar irrigation; nevertheless, the progression has not been as active as set, with only 46%. Falling short of its set now target of 150 MW, the wind power capacity produced 98 MW by 2020. Furthermore, the study of incorporating with the national grid whereby excess power can be returned back to the grid, the operation of solar irrigation pumps is being looked at, in the view of enhancing the revenue generation of the systems(Mainuddin, 2022). There are relative options to enhance the farming yield in the south-central coastal areas even in cases with a mild climate change affecting the region and its rivers where fresh water from the river surface can be utilized, which makes no harm to the salination of the rivers. Remote sensing

technology is also in the process of being employed to measure of areas where data is limited although ET is also being used to provide a reliable way of calculating the amount of irrigation required. But socio-cultural and political issues that affect the provision and distribution of water resources have posed challenges to the large-scale irrigation modernization projects which are being supported by foreign-based organizations such as the Asian Development Bank as noted by (Mainuddin, 2022). Although Bangladesh has significantly developed its irrigation system throughout the country, there are challenges that are related to technology adoption, sociopolitical aspect of the country and sustainability objectives.

Challenges in Irrigation in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, there are a number of hurdles that are inherent in the country's irrigation facility that hampers both the efficiency and sustainability of agriculture. Another issue is the quality of irrigation water; water quality has become an important issue in arid and semi-arid regions and as such, some places are unsuitable for irrigation due to high content of magnesium and potassium. In addition, unpredictability of impact of the surface water extraction on river saline, especially when climate change occurs complicates the prospects for agricultural development in the south-central coastal region (Mainuddin, 2022). This is evident in the production of Okra where automated micro irrigation techniques are presented still as unestablished techniques of improving use of water but conventional irrigation practices can greatly affect the percentage of water wastage (Zannat et al., 2023). These issues are aggravated by climate change which results to higher temperatures, irregular rainfall, and increase in salinity levels. These factors threaten rice production and demand for efficient irrigation practices and the variety that may withstand prominent stresses(Haque & Nahar, 2023). Another problem is that even the pressing irrigation requirements depend on the use of fossil fuels up to date. As for other off-grid solutions ,solar irrigation pumps are a feasible solution but grid connection and expenses are an

issue(Hossain et al., 2024). Water deterioration due to industrialisation particularly the tannery and textile industries can have a bearing on the availability of good quality water; both ground and surface water which is important for irrigation. In Bangladesh, the biggest environmental concern in peoples' recent memory is geogenic arsenic (As) contamination in shallow aquifer systems. Currently, the reported quantities in drinking water sources are higher than the WHO guideline of 10 µg/L which poses a perilous exposure to around 50 million people. Several researches have been carried out on As as it was first discovered in the groundwater of the southwest Bangladesh in early 1990s(Shamsudduha, 2013). The most significant issues or challenges that faced Bangladesh are given below:

Flooding

Being a country which is most sensitive to the impacts of climate change, Bangladesh has a serious issue in crop production due to flooding, particularly the region of the delta of the GBM basins. The phases and densities of cropping have altered over the years especially in the period from the late 1970s. As stated by (Uddin et al., 2019) the following are among the major causes of these changes include; Enhanced frequency and intensity of floods, elevated/extreme farming practices. Food security and income

sources are threatened by regular and heavy floods that are occasioned by climate change. Crops are very much affected by these floods and most of the agricultural fields are washed away. The geographical pattern demonstrated that built up area and cropland area are more vulnerable to flooding (Fig 1). The statistics of the croplands as well as populated areas affected by the 2020 floods are provided in (Figure 2). In Assam, 28.47% of croplands and 9.15% of built-up areas were impacted. Bihar saw 24.54% of croplands and 7.29% of built-up areas affected. In West Bengal, the floods impacted 24.63% of croplands and 5.66% of built-up areas. Meanwhile, in Bangladesh, 23.68% of croplands and 5.8% of built-up areas were affected by the floods(Pandey AC, 2022). Besides jute, aus, and aman, sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum*) appears to be a crop which tends to be flooded most often and most severely. This crop is planted during february and March of the preceding year while the harvesting takes place during January and February of the following year. From this, one can infer that floods may pose harm to the plants at the time when they are growing to their median size (Rasid & Paul, 1987). Whereas, LHU is needed for detailed agricultural and irrigation management, better weather and flood forecasts, as well as for sound land and water management(Ray, 2020).

Figure 1. The Effects of Flooding on LULC as Determined by Composite Maps Covering the Months of July through September
Source: Adapted and modified from Pandey AC, 2022.

Figure 2. Flood Impacts on Cropland and Built-Up Area

Source: Modified from Pandey AC, 2022

The agricultural environment in Bangladesh's Subarnachar upazila is under additional stress due to the conversion of mangrove forests to farmland and settlements due to changes in land use and land cover brought on by population pressure and the demand for food (Abdi et al., 2023). Croplands in Bangladesh's southwest have become marshy due to waterlogging, which has negatively impacted ecosystem services and biodiversity. This has resulted in low agricultural productivity and other socioeconomic problems (Ankhi & Rouf, 2023). Over 618 million people live in the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna river basin, which frequently floods during the yearly monsoon. Climate change is expected to make floods more frequent and severe, which will have long-term health effects like an increase in infant mortality in flood-prone areas (Rerolle et al., 2023). Significant effects on livelihoods, including damage to crop cultivation, fisheries, and poultry, have been seen in the Amrajuri union in the Pirojpur district of

Bangladesh, which is extremely vulnerable to natural disasters like cyclones and floods. As a result, people have been forced to adopt alternative livelihood practices and adaptation strategies (Akter et al., 2023).

Water Scarcity

Due to the water scarcity in Bangladesh, the country's agriculture is significantly challenged and this is detrimental to the farmer and the agriculture output. This paper reveals that besides resource indicators, water poverty involves political, social, economic and institutional aspects in the peri-urban areas of the Dhaka city. This leads to extreme poverty among the squeezed groups of the population such as elderly women and adolescent girls (Kibria & Abedin, 2022). Climate change also affects water shortage in addition to the sources of fresh water. The studies of future climatic conditions reveal that water stress would increase due to changed hydrological flows and increasing water demand for more than 875 million people of the SA, Bangladesh included (Kirby & Mainuddin, 2022). Reduction of salt and water logging in the coastal areas helps to retain the positive impact of the repairing work of the embankment but here poor are at a disproportionate loss (Rahman & Barua, 2023). While the catastrophic climatic scenarios may increase the angle of cropland vulnerable to the influence of the negative saline levels, there is the possibility of increasing agricultural productivity in the south-central coast region of the countries through the use of fresh water rivers for irrigation (Khan et al., 2023). The problem is they don't have sources of deep water and they are fully depended on some falls which are available for several months in a year and dries up in the winter time – these hill tract tribal people face acute water crises and it is a real hardship for them in many ways (Rafiqul Islam, 2022). That means, drought coupled with water scarcity or makes water scarcity even worse particularly in the areas that experience high level of droughts. This leads to reduced food production in agricultural activities, availability of food products, and cost which

affect the demand and marketing patterns as observed by (Hoque et al., 2022). The WEF complex in the MENA region proves the need for combined planning to cope with the shortage of water resources. This is especially realistic for Bangladesh which experiences the consequences of climate change in energy generation and increasing demand, as well as in agriculture (Chowdhury et al., 2022).

Climate Change

The paper reveals that Bangladesh's availability of irrigation water is significantly influenced by climate change through the following factors. Concerning precipitation, opinions vary, with some climate change models suggesting increased amounts and others suggesting decreased amounts in the future; consequently, the runoff and water availability will be ill-defined, rendering the nation's water resources very vulnerable (Huang, 2023). Because irrigation is highly dependent of groundwater which is already showing signs of being over exploited the northwest region which is vital for agriculture, is most at risk (Kamal et al., 2024). The problem is compounded by massive irrigation in regions such as Barind Tract area through the rapid come down of the groundwater table (Kamruzzaman et al., 2023). In addition, most of the nation demonstrates much lower trends of potential evapotranspiration (ET_o), which is so important for irrigation purposes. This may be due to fewer hours of sunshine and wind intensity though there is increased temperature (Uddin et al., 2023). Consequently, when it comes to water resource management as well as irrigation scheduling, the ET_o reduction mentioned above will be a challenge. Furthermore, extremely intense forms occasioned by climate change like cyclones and floods compound water structures and horticultural output reducing the reliability of proffering irrigation water in ordinary succession (Hussein, 2021; Olotu et al., 2022). In addition, the reduction of fresh water availability for irrigation by exacerbation of these occurrences, is the higher frequency and intensity of the latter causing higher rates of groundwater abstraction and saltwater intrusion in various parts of the world, particularly coastal

areas (Khan et al., 2023). The basins considered likely to experience large changes due to climate change include the Brahmaputra which is expected to experience discharge augmentations by the end of the century. This could somehow affect the stream flow and consequently the availability of water for agricultural use at different years (Mainuddin, 2022).

Environmental Degradation

The problem of environmental degradation in irrigation technology in Bangladesh transpired: pesticide use, water quality, and the pondering of the adoption of an efficient irrigation system. Another major social implication is the effects of Groundwater Irrigation to the environment where more areas within the northern regions section have tapped into the water resource. Some of such challenges include, losing the water tables and energy utilization due to the use of diesel and electricity by the pump (Islam et al., 2022). The above problem receives a boost of concern due to pesticide residues that end up in water bodies, specifically carbamate and organophosphorus chemicals which are very toxic to aquatic life and health hazardous to human beings (Parvin et al., 2022). As a result of As poisoning in the GW used for irrigation and drinking, this carcinogenic metalloid has accumulated in the crops, especially the rice, as part of the food chain and has long-term health effects (Rahman et al., 2023). Similar to the dangers of high salt content, and medium salinity, there are similar impacts on the nutrient dynamics of the sectors associated with shrimp processing and the need for proper management to moderate the salinity, pH, and hardness content of the water. In addition, pollution from the wastewater containing heavy metals and other pollutants in the important rivers such as Buriganga, Karnaphuli, and others has impaired water quality and rendered the water unsuitable for irrigation purposes; and heavy metals accumulate in fishes and in crops (Rashid et al., 2023). Despite little changes to the rice yield, some practices such as the AWD – an irrigation technique involving wetting and drying the field in turn, have indicated to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases especially methane. This indicates that there could be a way towards

better practice of irrigations which would not be quite as damaging to the ecosystems as the current procedures.

Major Irrigation System in the World

There are 2 categories of irrigation system: Gravity fed system and Pressurized system.

Gravity Fed System

Among the methods of distributing water for the use in agriculture, the sustainable and feasible technique that can be used in areas that are scarce of water supplies is the gravity irrigation system. They are not characterized by the use of energy demanding pumps because the force of gravity is harnessed to facilitate the movement of water from the source location to the fields. For instance, manganese concentration and its consequent biofilm growth within the pipes reduces hydraulic capability and quantitative delivery of water at Blyderiver dam in South Africa, which uses gravity irrigation. Despite their vulnerability to urbanisation and climate change, this type of conventional systems remain in use across the Mediterranean for the creation of wetlands and replenishment of aquifers (Saxena, 2021). Drip irrigation from a gravity feed has also grown in its popularity especially in the third world nations due to efficiency in the use of water. Research on low-cost drip irrigation kits for the Philippines erupted that the emitter discharge rates and uniformly water distribution made them eligible for small-scale farming as they remained stable at a variety of heads (Martinez et al., 2022). Yield increases up to 43 percent have been seen with the application of the described techniques. 3 t/ha and water consumption ranging from 68 to 98%. 1%, gravity fed drip fertigation systems have shown to enhance the production of the crops along with the consumption of the water and the fertilizers along with the profitability of the high value crops (Patra & Poddar, 2022).

Pressurized System

Due to the fact they raise crop yield and water efficiency, pressured irrigation systems comprising of drip and sprinkler approaches

become vital to modern agriculture. But on the other hand, there are a lot of advantages and issues connected with functioning of these systems as well. Thus, to identify areas for improvement and suggest changes that may lead to potential reductions in costs and increased system reliability for example, the COPAM program has been applied to analyze and improve the performance of pressurized irrigation systems that are used in agriculture (Kanimozhi & Vadivel, 2024). In a similar manner, there is an online tool developed for the designing and optimizing of the primary pipe in these systems to ensure they are properly and accurately designed, and also while using them is easy even for non-technical end users (Bonet & Yubero, 2024). While it enhances the yield and density of crops; transition from surface irrigation systems to the pressurized types has been proved to enhance the depletion and demand for water with variability in the real evapotranspiration rates. Energy is one of the most important problems since pressured systems require lots of energy to operate. It has been noted that by the deployment of SCADA systems and the proper adjustments of its setup together with the increasing speed of electric pumps one can save as much as 16% of the energy being consumed. Other enhancing measures like adjusting the motor frequencies and the branch pipe queues can achieve an energy conservation of up to 19%. Pumps-as-turbines (PATs), that generate electricity by utilization of surplus pressure can also be incorporated to enhance the systems sustainability and reliability. The extent of these system's efficiency and sustainability can be further enhanced by developing innovative strategies such as the green valve for dynamic control and continual monitoring. In addition, by providing information regarding a 42-year-old patient with a poorly controlled type 2 diabetes mellitus, the significance of self-monitoring blood glucose and aggression to maintain glycemic control is also illustrated. reduction of energy usage by 51% in experimental areas, it is suggested that concept of intelligent control system founded on fuzzy logic may reduce the consumption of water and power by a significant margin. It is possible to

attach another level of optimization if practicing the usage of smart irrigation systems that can independently determine the optimum amount of moisture in the soil and turn the water supply on and off without people's intervention (Saxena, 2021). Thus, pressurized irrigation systems are a viable solution for sustainable agriculture in water-deficit countries because of the yields, water, and possibly energy advantages of pressurized systems. Yet it requires more capital investment and operating cost in the beginning as compared to the single plant investment. Thus, to maximize or fully utilizes these systems advantages and at the same time reducing or avoiding these systems disadvantages, advanced technologies and optimization method needs to be methodologies to be develop and implemented.

Types of Irrigation Techniques

Surface Irrigation

Surface irrigation systems involve the use of gravity to deliver water on and across the land to wet and/ or permeate the ground (Figure 3). This method entail furrow irrigation where water is used to flow in ditches beside the crop rows mostly are used in vegetables and corn crop. Border strip irrigation is the water running in strips that are separated by ridges and is best for fields that are slightly sloped and all types of crops. Basin irrigation inundates level basins with earth bunds suitable for growing water demanding crops like rice. The system is called flood irrigation when water is spread over the whole field and is common in areas with flat land and plenty of water; however, it is rather ineffective as too much water is used. Soil management plays an important role optimizing water used on the surface and land leveling is therefore important to control water loss.

Drip Irrigation

Drip irrigation or trickle irrigation provides water in a drop by drop fashion at the root level of the plants and manages to be one of the most water efficient irrigation methods when properly managed (Figure 4). It does not allow evaporation or runoff hence helping in water

conservation. In the present day usage, especially with plastic mulch which also helps in further decreasing evaporation, it also acts as the means through which fertilizers can be delivered.

Figure 3. Surface Irrigation in Bangladesh
Source: https://www.google.com/search?q=surface+irrigation+in+Bangladesh&scas_esv

Figure 4. Drip Irrigation Technology in Bangladesh
Source: https://www.google.com/search?q=Drip+irrigation+system+in+Bangladesh&scas_esv

Sprinkler Irrigation

Sprinkler or overhead irrigation refers to conveying water through pipes to central points of a field and then using high pressure sprinklers or guns to release the water in the field (Figure 5). Sprinkler, spray, or gun type which are fixed and have permanently erected risers are termed as the solid-set irrigation systems. Rotors, which are high-pressure rotating sprinklers, work on ball drive, gear drive or impact drive. Besides the watering, guns are employed in such uses as dust control, and lumbering. It is also possible to install mobile versions of sprinklers with the central connection to water sources by means of

hoses. There are self-propelling wheeled devices, called traveling sprinklers, which may water small farming lands, soccer fields, gardens, pasturage, and cemeteries without the need for a control from people.

Figure 5. Sprinkler Irrigation System

Source: https://www.google.com/search?q=sprinkler+irrigation+in+Bangladesh&sc_esv

Figure 6. Localized Irrigation

Source: https://www.google.com/search?q=localized+irrigation+picture&sc_esv

Localized Irrigation

This technique uses low pressure of water through pipelines and then plan the patterning of the water flow then directing the water small portions onto each plant or nearby. These include drip irrigation system which is used allows water to drip in the plant root area only, spray irrigation system another method that is used with the intention of allowing water to spray at the required areas only, this is

accompanied by micro sprinkler irrigation system that is only used to ensure that water is delivered at the required areas only for effectiveness of the plants.

Sub-Surface Drip Irrigation

SDI is the best technique for the control of water resources in Bangladesh due to the increasing scarcity of water and emphasis on organic farming (Figure 7). SDI systems are important because they help any area that has little water such as Bangladesh in this case to use water in the right manner since majority of the water is delivered to the root zone of plants therefore little wastage through evaporation as well as runoff. Researches indicate that SDI might significantly enhance crop output and water consumption rate. It is particularly true for Bangladesh as usually conventional method of irrigation leads to high losses of water in the region. Moreover, it can also be shown that SDI systems help in promoting a better distribution of water on the soil surfaces, and thus reduces nutrient leaching, which in turn helps a lot in maintaining the fertility of the soil and the overall health of the same (Arefin, (2022, November).; Saxena, 2021). Just like the findings that were derived from investigation on the effects of long-term SDI usage on such plants as decorative grass plots and others; the organic matter, nutrient status of the soil was not compromised; thus, the application of SDI in urban landscaping and agricultural fields will similarly assist in enhancing the ecological health of the soil (Saxena, 2021). Cropping systems that have adopted the use of SDI systems are also immune to the climatic fluctuations since they cutout nitrogen as well as drought pressures. The assimilation of SDI systems with Conservation Agriculture techniques can had a better impact on Food Yield and Water Conservation. For example, from the analysis of both potentials water and crop yield amidst the SDI conservation agriculture technique in the South Asian region, it has been made crystal clear that the technique reduces on evaporation and deep drainage losses hence enhancing on biomass yield as well as the cumulative root water intake (Saxena, 2021). On this aspect of selective crop control, SDI has been found to be relatively

effective on certain crops especially the cotton crops. Evidence has indicated that it increases Nitrogen Use Efficiency, Water Use Efficiency and seed cotton yield as compared to surface flood irrigation(Hati et al., 2022). Research has proven that with regard to water conservation, cost of labor for watering and maintenance, SDI has a higher edge over standard sprinkler system(Arefin, (2022, November).). This same manuscript thus brings out the likelihood of using it in landscape irrigation. Also, with the use of such technologies as the Subsurface Drip Fertigation Estimation Tool (SubFerT), farmers can get the best out of water and fertilizer application hence making the SDI system more efficient and easier to use(Saxena, 2021). In any case, benefits of SDI in the context of Bangladesh imply greatly enhanced level of crop yields, soil fertility and water effective, which qualify for the choice of efficient and sustainable landscaping and farming in the region.

Figure 7. Sub-Surface Drip Irrigation

Source: https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/en/v/iwrm/Implementation/technical_measures/Irrigation-systems/subsurface_irrigation/index.html

Drip Irrigation

The often application of water through drip irrigation whereby water is delivered at the plant root level has been observed to have a lot of great prospects in increasing agricultural productivity in Bangladesh. Typically in the nation, so many traditional practices of irrigation pull out large volumes of water that are not required hence improving water use efficiency is paramount in enhancing productivity, especially

for important foods such as okra(Saxena, 2021). which is highly valuable economically. Efficiency when it comes to water usage may be improved by the following applications that include timed micro irrigation techniques such as the drip irrigation which has been proven to save water by as much as 11% more than the conventional practices. The agricultural industry of Bangladesh indeed holds the significant importance as it involves the more than 47% of the country's working population and contributes nearly to 12% of the GDP; therefore, the use of the drip irrigation system becomes even more relevant. It has been noted that proper irrigation methods are important tool for continued expansion of agriculture especially in the context of climate change and changes in rainfall and flow in the upstream sections. Through exploitation and management of aquifers for dry season irrigation Bangladesh has become food secured country. This has created the possibility of growing tons of rice, a method that also enhances the recharge of the ground water during the rainy season. For instance, the management of drip irrigation system in banana farming may lead to water saving ranging between 30 to 45 percent. 62% showing that the technique works,(Saxena, 2021). Yields and production outcomes are better due to the drip irrigation system's capacity to apply resources and fertilizer and water in a well-measured and controlled manner without evaporating, percolating deeply or leaking from the pipes(Arefin, (2022, November).). Indeed, this approach is rather useful in the regions that experience a drought period and where availability and quality of water are crucial questions. Researched has shown that after some of the surface water and some of the groundwater are good sources of water for irrigation in these areas, Most of the water used for irrigation is of good quality to be used. Mild climate change indicators for the south central coastal zone show the possibility of significantly raising the yield of agricultural production by irrigating with river water with no changes in river salinity(Khan et al., 2023). However, there still is the debate on the effectiveness of supplementary watering. Some research shows that there are no significant yield increases and

lower profitability; this shows that future projects must take this fact into consideration (Rahman & Connor, 2024). In Bangladesh it has evidence that it is a good tool for enhancing crop production and efficient use of water through drip irrigation but its take and impacts are voluntary agriculture crops and areas. Drip irrigation can minimize the huge wastages of water that conventional irrigation methods, which are applied in the country often, create. A meta-analysis of the worldwide literature comparing drip irrigation with overhead irrigation types such as flood, border, and furrow irrigation in general averted that drip

irrigation provided water and food security and promise of agricultural productiveness with proven yield increments of up to 28 percent. 92% under ideal circumstances (Saxena, 2021). Rice is one of the most consumed crops in Bangladesh. Studies have revealed that the AWD irrigation that is a type of drip irrigation technique can save about 24% of water and enhance water productivity by 224% in Chattogram and Feni district (Given in the tables 2 and Figure 3). It can also marginally raise the production of paddy by 3 percentage points in comparison with continuous flooding (Hossain & Islam, 2022).

Table 2. Shows How Irrigation Techniques Affect the Amount of Water Required and the Water Productivity of Paddy Fields in the Chattogram and Feni Districts

Metric	Feni (CF)	Feni (AWD)	Chattogram (CF)	Chattogram (AWD)
Number of Irrigations (ha ⁻¹)	85	65	73	56
Amount of Irrigation (m ³ ha ⁻¹)	5152.7	3872.9	4454.5	3381.7
Water Productivity (kg m ⁻³)	0.47	1.71	0.52	1.50

Source: Adapted and modified from Hossain & Islam, 2022

Note: CF: Conventional flooding; AWD: Alternate Wetting and Drying

Besides, the use of mechanized systems such as FN & N systems in the practice of irrigation has been proved to conserve water by up to 50 – 60 % this is very important in the conserve of fresh water resource as well as the costs of energy (Saxena, 2021). Supplemental irrigation which is a type of drip irrigation has been claimed to be very useful, though, as major statistical analyses of real farm performance of the adopters in Bangladesh, mainly shows that the adopters have had lower profitability rates than non-adopters and no indications of yield enhancement. Nevertheless, research on the environmental impacts of the safe withdrawal of SW for irrigation in the southern central coastal region has shown that only moderate climate change results in (i) negligible changes in the river water salinity; (ii) hence, it is possible to significantly expand irrigated crops production without harm to the environment (Khan et al., 2023).

Drawback of Drip Irrigation

Listed below are some of the disadvantages of drip irrigation even though it is a water saving method. The setting up expenses may be very attractive primarily because of the application of emitters, tube and pumps among others. Another major problem is maintenance, the small emitters utilized in drip systems are susceptible to blockage from the soil particles, algae and mineral build up to block the system, meaning constant cleaning and monitoring is required. Drip irrigation on the other hand may also be less efficient in delivering water on sloped land if not well regulated and planned for. Also, these systems need adequate and qualitative water supply as any pollution may result in clogging and hence minimization of the systems efficiency. Finally, because water is deposited on the soil surface the salts from the water do not leach into the root zone as this causes soil salinity especially if not controlled.

Figure 8. Irrigation Techniques' Effect on the Yield Attributes and Paddy Yield at Feni and Chattogram

Source: Adapted and modified from Hossain & Islam, 2022

History of Drip Irrigation

In a relatively long time, drip irrigation which is of method designed to increase luminaries productivity with less water input, has evolved significantly. Drip irrigation system was originally designed to solve water scarcity and improve the methods of irrigation. They have

since then been applied on several fields of agricultural settings. The main rationale behind the technique is to supply water to a plant at the root zone, hence, minimizing waste from evaporation and other effects. This is especially so in arid areas and areas experiencing water shortage and this is especially where the

provision of safe and sufficient water is a major challenge (Bai et al., 2022). One of the prominent systems that have benefited agriculture is drip irrigation; especially in the Sub-Saharan Africa. However, poor links such as supply chains and poor technical knowledge in farming among the farmers have been some of the barriers to the expansion of this technique (Pal et al., 2023). The drip irrigation has revealed that it has huge benefits over other conventional irrigation methods such as floods and furrow irrigation and has played a significant role to made use in the area of China to improve crop growth and physiology quality, yield and water usage efficiency (Yang et al., 2023). A number of studies perviously done in Indonesia suggest that drip irrigation may greatly reduce the irrigation time and water use which in turn increases the crop yield and reduces cost of production (Cartika et al., 2023). The system has also been redesigned for use in the forest nurseries to help subsequently reduce the costs of fertilizers and to improve the quality of the irrigation system. (Bai et al., 2022). Technological advancements also include the experimenting of a new design of an emitter to overcome hitches such as this clogging which would otherwise reduce the performance of any system. For instance, research carried out on different emitter sorts has established that blockage can reduce the flow rate from 85% to 89% (Almeida et al., 2022). Other cost effective emitters include novel materials that have shown favourable results concerning hydraulic conductivity and water discharge rate which include sago fronds (Bansal et al., 2021). To enhance the outcomes of drip irrigation systems, statistical models have also been developed with an aim of fine-tuning the wetting pattern in different types of soils (Pal et al., 2023). It has also been observed through long-term experiments how drip irrigation influences the soil and its Microbial community and the stability of the soil aggregate which is very critical in the sustainable cropping system (Dahiya et al., 2022). Also, cheap drip irrigation systems have been manufactured for enhancing the abilities of female farmers in the underdeveloped countries and give them the effective instruments to control the small-scale agricultural

production (Ghosh et al., 2022). Thus, it can be stated that the history of drip irrigation can be divided into several aspects marked with continuous improvement and development that have been driven by the need to enhance agriculture yields and address the problem of water shortage across the globe. Since technology is a tool to preserve the environment and food security is a result of advanced technology, the advancement in technology depicts a positive advancement in the farming practices.

Advantages of Drip Irrigation

Drip irrigation therefore is a common important and ecological method in the modern agriculture as it has more benefits compared to the conventional methods of irrigation. One of the main advantages of this system is intensive ability to save water. Simple methods of water delivery such as drip irrigation help minimize wastage and runoff since the water directly gets to the plants' root section; this is advantageous especially where water is scarce (Al-Sharify et al., 2023; Kapoor et al., 2022). While comparing it to the other common methods such as floods or irrigation sprinkler systems, this practice is likely to use between 40 percent less water (Moursy et al., 2023). In addition, since the water and nutrients are applied in the correct and equal measures, the drip irrigation enhances yield of crops by promoting root development and improved nutrient absorption (Bai et al., 2022; Paramesha et al., 2022). For instance, studies show that drip irrigation may increase the yield of crops by 14%. 55% when compared to border irrigation and by 28% when compared to earthen check basin irrigation. than flooding irrigation by 92 percent. As mentioned by (Al-Sharify et al., 2023) the following effects include a decrease in the salinity of the soil and in the use of fertilizers that leach through the soil hence enhancing the soil quality as well as its sustainability. Thus, the drip refrigeration – a technique that involves the use of drip irrigation and applying fertilizers increases resources efficiency as the nutrients reach the plant roots. This, in turn, leads to a cut in fertilizer by 15 – 25%, and lower production costs as a beneficial effect. In this regard, this technique also improves the chemical, biological,

and physical properties of the soil thereby supporting crop growth and yield (Bai et al., 2022). Drip irrigation systems are also very flexible and applicable for all type of crops including cotton, wheat, vegetables, and horticulture crops (Bansal et al., 2021). The method is valuable for areas with salty water shortage and salinity issues in particular in dry and semi-arid regions of the world since the technique does not harm crop production while using the available salty water effectively (Moursy et al., 2023). In addition, drip irrigation systems are developed in advance as low-pressure and low volume and thus is energy saver and water saver and therefore they can be ecological and cost effective. Besides protecting crops from drought stress, the cycle of regulating the levels of soil moisture assures smooth and never ceasing agricultural output (Cartika et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2023). Some advantages of drip irrigation include use reduced water, increased production, minimized on use of fertilizers, improved soil texture, flexibility with regard to the type of crops and geographical location, and cost effective. For this reasons, the application of drip irrigation represents a wonderful solution in the fight against world's water shortage and climate change in agriculture.

Drip Irrigation for Arid and Semi-Arid Soil

Thus, in the dry and semi-arid regions for instance the zones of Bangladesh where water scarcity coupled with high salinity in the soil makes it difficult especially for agriculture the drip irrigation proves to be very effective when it comes to the management of the scares water resources. Micro irrigation systems like drip irrigation has a possibility of increasing production and water use efficiency by many folds. An example of what could be the benefits of the optimum water in similar conditions are the Egypt, where DI in the level of 80 % of IWR contributed to the enhancement of the productions of sugar-beet, WUE and decrease of the nematode damages (Bansal et al., 2021). In the case of the Barind Tract, the Barind Multipurpose Development Authority (BMDA) that has undertaken measures such as deep tube well installation and reexcavation of water bodies to supplement the surface water used for

irrigation has by its measures brought about positive change in the scenario of Barind Tract whereby groundwater recharge has been enhanced and the losses of water have equally been minimized (Yang et al., 2023). Standard quality of water used in irrigation is very important since poor quality water affects the quality of soil in the farm. The water quality indices like irrigation water quality index (IWQI) and fuzzy irrigation water quality index (FIWQI) reveal very high appropriateness for use in irrigation and different studies carried in Bangladesh have shown that a vast majority of irrigation water are fit for use. As proved in the case of the dry areas, using drip irrigation below mulch is effective in enhancing groundwater recharge and infiltration depths, which is of significance for maintaining the general moisture status of the soil (Dahiya et al., 2022). Moreover, when sprinkering is adjusted by the exact moisture state of the soil, and in combination with sensor-based drip irrigation, the latter minimizes water use. Some challenges include; Thus, the problems such as capital intensity at the start of establishing these systems and technical details must be solved before many small-scale farmers will embrace these systems (Tan et al., 2023). It has been beneficial in China where after three years of drip irrigation in the Hetao Irrigation District, the average of; the decreased salinity in the soil and the percentage of plant survival; illustrates the effectiveness of drip irrigation (Şahin, 2023). It indicates that for efficient water distribution it is necessary to create wetting zones under drip irrigation system. Thus, such models as Hydrus-2D, which can predict the radius and depth of wetting based on parameters of irrigation and properties of the soil, can help in designing effective irrigation (Pal et al., 2023). Also, other studies that has been carried out on spring maize in desert NW China revealed that drip fertigation which also incorporates a method of irrigation as well as fertilization help in proper distribution of nutrients and thus increase crop production (Al-Sharify et al., 2023). Finally, according to (Fan et al., 2023), since the drip irrigation properly controls the amount of fertilizer supplied to the plants, the cases of nitrogen leaching, which are common when using conventional irrigation

systems, can be minimized. Drip irrigation therefore is a viable strategy for sustainable agriculture in such harsh environment because it can in general contribute to considerable improvement in water use efficiency, soil status, and crop yield in combination with the application of sustainable technologies in the expanding arid and semi-arid zones of Bangladesh.

Surface Drip Irrigation

Surface drip irrigation (SDI) is another efficient irrigation technique using emitters that substantially raise crop yield and water productivity by delivering water to plants' roots. In a dry and semi-arid region hence this technique is very useful since the rationing of water is very vital. Research has showed that using SDI, one can obtain high water distribution uniformity, the coefficients of which (CU) may be up to 97.02 percent after system upgrades; certify crops receive steady water supply (Seyar & Ahamed, 2023). More specifically, unlike other conventional types of irrigation such as furrow irrigation, SDI either maintains or increases crop productivity with much less water. For instance, in a case of research on maize, SDI provided a yield of 10,200 kg/ha as compared to 9,175 kg/ha of furrow irrigation using water of only 1,452 m³/ha (Liu et al., 2023). In addition, research carried out shows that SDI systems could cut down ammonia vaporization by as much as 76.40%, in this way reducing nitrogen loss and enhancing soil fertility (Ma et al., 2023). The opportunity to increase the growth and yield of crops in conditions of deficiency irrigation also stands on the approach. For instance, in arid zones and conditions, invariably where water availability is likely to be an issue, SDI enabled sorghum to maintain excellent water productivity when watered at 70 – 80 percent of irrigation efficiency maximums without yield loss; evidence of the system's utility (Sun et al., 2024). In addition, there is also apparent influence of SDI on the nitrogen cycle as well as the bacterial content in the soil. It reasons that it generates a more constant moisture condition near to the root area, which has an influence on the health of the soil and nutrients that

influences the change in microbial biomass and community according to (Griffin-LaHue et al., 2023). In addition, there is also apparent influence of SDI on the nitrogen cycle as well as the bacterial content in the soil. It reasons that it generates a more constant moisture condition near to the root area, which has an influence on the health of the soil and nutrients that influences the change in microbial biomass and community according to (Ma et al., 2023). Likewise, when knowledge in the irrigation volume and lateral burial depth were enhanced, and the alfalfa watered with SDI was shown to have enhanced, water consumption, yield, water productivity. However, SDI systems as mentioned earlier could be tailored for all these crop needs and the specific circumstances of the environment. Compared to the other irrigation methods, SDI trained lettuces to yield the best and field water usage efficiency thus showing that it is effective in different situations System. After analyzing for all relevant factors, it can be concluded that SDI is a practical and efficient method of irrigation which might help to increase crop yield but use water efficiently, thus SDI can be a useful tool in modern farming (Jing et al., 2023; Şahin, 2023).

Challenges and Constraints of Drip Irrigation

Thus, although there are practically no rivals to drip irrigation in terms of efficiency and effective use of less water, there are some problems and drawbacks that do not let this technology spread. Some of these problems encompass; To start with, cost of assets consumption is significantly high for subsurface drip irrigation (SDI) which is out of reach for small scale farmers and even those in the low and middle income nations as pointed by (Yang et al., 2023). Moreover, what are termed emitter clogging issues, which indicate a more serious situation as emitter clogging and need very effective filtering to maintain the performance; for instance, using fish farm drainage water as a water source (Derbala et al., 2023). Nevertheless, design and management of drip irrigation system entail some challenges. For instance, depending on the design of the emitter, it maybe non-pressure compensated, thus, requires a close check on

local head loss and flow-rate changes in order to regulate water distribution along longer lateral lines (Pal et al., 2023). In intelligent drip irrigation systems, the conventional PID control systems face some problems associated with nonlinearity and time varying. In order to enhance the standard of the system, further enhancing the stability and performance, there is a need for better algorithms some of which are as follows. Since drip lines are directional and cannot have water flow rates changed along one line, another difficult task in drip systems is the defining of management zones for VRI is another difficult task that requires optimisation models to achieve the best of water productivity (Zhang & Song, 2023). The author (Li et al., 2024) study published highlighted that irrigation with wastewater calls health and toxicity concerns. Thus, the proper technologies have to be used in irrigation, like sub-surface drip systems, thus minimizing the threat of pollution. Looking at water use efficiency and yield status under such irrigation conditions, the irrigation schedules and designs having to be fine-tuned through other models such as HYDRUS 2D/3D and AquaCrop. In the same context, climate change worsens these tensions through the impacts it poses on food security and water resources (Djalilov et al., 2023; Mohammed et al., 2023). However, these are the drawback of drip irrigation system still applicable for sustainable agriculture particularly rain fed or in arid and semi-arid areas in view of the fact that it reduces water wastage and increase crop yield in the right application of the system as indicated by (Al-Sharif et al., 2023). However, these problems require additional scientific investigation to increase the performance and sustainability of drip irrigation systems worldwide.

Prospects of Smart Irrigation in Bangladesh

It is suggested that the smart farming be applied in Bangladesh so that responsible leadership may go for sustainable agriculture other than relying on the application of the conventional farming and the irrigation techniques.

Figure 9. Smart Irrigation System Overview
Source: Adapted and modified from Khaled Obaideen a 2022

The above discussed sources of water like surface water, ground water and rainfall if used for irrigation is very wasteful in nature in Bangladesh. Due to the poor and outdated irrigation system, 25 % – 30 % of the water is utilized for irrigation (Afroj et al., 2016). In some sectors of Bangladesh, there has been an application of water-based irrigation commonly termed as AWD, standing for alternate wetting and drying. Thus, when assessing the water depth or water source in a field located beneath the ground surface, AWD might use a PVC pipe or tube (Pearson et al., 2018). Previous studies have noted that AWD approach is roughly 365 mm or 27% saving in irrigation water compared to the traditional methods (Matese et al., 2015). These two are parameters that define the amount and presence of water on the leaf surface known as the leaf wetness. This is because water is typically acquired from rain, dew, and/or fog and as a result is usually found on a plant's leaf. In addition, the plant may develop water logged leaves if the plant is over watered (Balendonck et al., 2008). Bangladesh can address the issues of hunger and sustainable agriculture of the UN SDGs by 2030 with the help of connected AI IoT smart farming techniques (Haque et al., 2018). Thus, intelligent technologies are ideal for the sensitisation of sustainable agriculture in Bangladesh. A possible plan for deploying the smart sprinkler system using the concepts of smart things in distant smart farming through Internet of Things and LoRaWAN was presented by the researchers (Pasandideh, 2020).

Conclusion

Techniques of the irrigation in Bangladesh has seen certain changes but the challenges which were existing from the past are still there and to make a sustainable production in the agriculture sectors attention should be given. Earlier, Bangladesh changed from surface water irrigation to ground water irrigation system which in fact accelerated the overall enhancement in agricultural yields that moulded food self adequacy an accomplishment by the 1990's. Nonetheless, when change of use of the resource has taken this type of irrigation, the

resource has been extended with the vice of exhaustion of the ground water source as the main issue. Explaining the contemporary development of irrigation amidst the old technique and modern practices concerning this presents the understanding of how the process is in a steady process of changing, where the emphasis is increasing towards the/minimizing water use, efficiency and dealing with the effects of climatic change. Nevertheless, the current scenario of Bangladesh shows that the country has to go a long way to make Agriculture sustainable. Hence, a regular exploitation of the aquifers has led to the dramatic diminution of the water tables especially in the districts such as Barind Tract where the application of irrigation methods has enhanced the water stress. Further on, climate change which has calamitous consequences for societies contributed such features as; erratication of rainfall, increase of the number of extreme weathers and temperatures means that irrigation systems are a challenge. These issues have placed it in a balance of the population's demand for food against the shortage of water leading to pressure on the country's agriculture.

The present day methods of irrigation highlighted by drip irrigation and the use of micro irrigation as a means of automating the process present a solution to achieving this feat. These are ideal technologies for the counties that are facing dry and semi arid climatic conditions within the region where the water resource is a limited one. But the usage of such technologies is not without challenge. Big capital, high incidences of failure and specialised skills required for their use present difficulties; especially for smallholder farmers who are the mainstay of Bangladesh Agriculture. However, the enhancement in water use productivity that has been evidenced by drip irrigation also arise scenario such as the quality of the water and maintenance of the particular system particularly in relatively high level salinities or poor water quality. In total, to eliminate such difficulties, it is necessary to adopt suitable policies and practices, develop and use information technologies, and design and perform human resource development

strategies. Thus to ensure sustainable water management in Bangladesh the government of Bangladesh has to come forward and irrigate more area properly that can be done only if emphasis is laid on research and development works in efficient use of water in different agro climatic areas. This also includes issues like promoting smart irrigation systems meant for the delivery of conserved water efficiency through real-time data and advanced sensors among others. There is also a need to invest on farmer education and extension so that farmers will be knowledgeable on the information and inputs that would enable them to properly adopt these technologies.

Hence, one might state that though the certain progress Bangladesh is to gain in order to set higher levels of irrigation it is a challenging road. What is important, the constantly growing rates of agricultural production and rational water management still remain a challenge, the resolution of which should imply constant advancement and alterations. This paper makes the following recommendations: First of all, the urgency of modernizing the irradiation of facilities is realized; secondly, the need to come up with better policies for agriculture is established; and lastly, there is the need to ensure that the human resource in the agricultural sectors and the related fields have adequate knowledge on the best practices most especially in the current atmospheric conditions. However, the above vision can be realized only and equally IF government, industrialists, academics and especially farmers are to unite and start pulling. Therefore, only with the help of such a partnership can Bangladesh wait for the necessary guarantees for the agricultural sector and further evolution towards sustainable.

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